

POTENTIAL FOR EQUAL EDUCATION QUALITY OF THE POOR THROUGH PHILANTHROPIC INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract

Indonesia Juara Foundation is a philanthropic institution in Indonesia that plays an active role in the distribution of quality education. Equitable quality education is carried out through scholarship programs and free schools. Education is the main capital in improving community welfare. The availability of good and equitable education can generate superior, innovative, and able to compete internationally. Every element in Indonesia is responsible for the distribution of education, especially for the poor. Not apart from the big role of philanthropic institutions in realizing equal distribution of educational rights that are good and evenly distributed in Indonesia. The research method used is a qualitative approach with a research design in the form of case studies. Data collection techniques were used in the form of non-participatory observation techniques, in-depth interviews, and research documentation, as well as secondary data collection from the Indonesian Juara Foundation (IJF). The analysis was carried out in the form of a descriptive analysis of the role of the Indonesian Juara Foundation institution as a flantropy institution engaged in the equal distribution of the quality of education in Indonesia. This study found a form of the role of the Indonesian Juara Foundation as a flantropy institution in Indonesia that succeeded in realizing the quality distribution of education for the poor through education empowerment programs. The results of these findings can be a guideline for the implementation of philanthropic institutions in Indonesia to create the availability of quality education for the poor.

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1. Introduction

The Central Statistics Agency (BPS) in 2016 stated that Indonesia experienced a growth in the Human Development Index (HDI) reaching 0.91%. This figure is 0.63 points higher than the 2015 HDI of 69.55%. The achievement of the HDI itself is measured in three aspects, including longevity and healthy age, knowledge, and a good standard of living.¹

The role of education in the improvement of the HDI can be seen from the increase in the average school duration expectation during the period 2010-2016 of 2.12%. In addition, the average length of schooling for people aged 25 years and over experienced a growth of 1.09% in the period 2010-2016. This indicates that the increasing number of long-term school expectations will increase the number of people who carry out compulsory education in Indonesia.²

Education is one of the biggest investments for a country. The low quality of human resources has a significant impact on the progress of the country itself.³ Quality human resources are the driving force of the country's economy in the ideal direction. The consequence of achieving this goal requires an effort to improve the quality of education to reduce the gap in education levels between group.

Equitable education in Indonesia has been stated in the 1945 Constitution, Article 28c, paragraph (1) which reads "everyone has the right to develop themselves through the fulfillment of their basic needs, the right to education and benefit from science and technology, art and culture, in order to improve the quality of life. and for the welfare of mankind".⁴ It means that education is a basic right for every citizen, and education must be accessible to anyone

Even so, Indonesia is still experiencing problems in the world of education, especially with regard to equal distribution of public access to affordable, quality, and competitive education.⁵ Based on the results of the International Program for International Student Assessment (PISA) international test in 2015, Indonesia experienced an improvement in the quality of education with 22.1 points, but Indonesia was still ranked lowest, ranking 63rd out of 72 countries surveyed.⁶

The inequality of Indonesian education can also be seen from the high number of school dropouts. Although the charts have declined over the past three years, from the 2015/2016 academic year to the 2017/2018 school year. The underlying problem behind this phenomenon is economic problems. The problem is that if the economy of a family can be said to be low, the education process will be hampered, considering that education costs tend to rise from year to year.⁷

Indeed education is the responsibility of all elements of the state, including the government, academics, companies (through CSR programs), non-governmental institutions, and the general public. One of the non-governmental organizations that took part in efforts to equalize the quality of education in Indonesia was the Indonesia Juara Foundation.

Indonesia Juara Foundation is a channeling partner of Rumah Zakat engaged in education empowerment. Rumah Zakat itself is a flantropy institution in Indonesia that has a role as a collector of zakat funds, infaq, alms, and other social funds. There are two benefits in the Islamic philanthropic institution, the first usefulness, namely in the individual with the desire to change for each individual towards a better direction, reflected in the effort to feed the human being from a bad character such as greed and stingy. The second benefit, namely social usefulness that is with the existence of philanthropic institutions will change the social order in building a culture of shared responsibility and increased welfare together (Uyun, 2015). At present, the existence of the flantropy institutions in Indonesia is very calculated, considering that 85% of the population of this country is Muslim. If all Muslims in Indonesia have a high awareness of the virtues of *zakat*, *infaq*, and alms, then this will be a great potential to help people unable to obtain quality education rights.⁸

Rumah Zakat distributes funds deposited by donors through four program areas, including a healthy smile (empowerment in the health sector), an independent smile (empowerment in the economic field), a sustainable smile (empowerment in the environmental field), and a Juara smile (empowerment in education).⁹ Through social funds that have been collected and managed professionally by the Zakat House, Indonesia Juara Foundation is the channeling and implementing agency in implementing the fund. Distribution and implementation are carried out to provide free access to education for disadvantaged communities throughout Indonesia through several programs, one of which is the Sekolah Juara program. Until 2018, 18 Sekolah Juara have been established consisting of 15 elementary schools, 2 junior high schools, and 1 vocational school spread in several major cities in Indonesia. The existence of the Sekolah Juara gets positive responses from the surrounding community. This can be seen from the number of enthusiasts who have increased since the beginning of its establishment until now. The thing that interests the community is even though this school is not paid but the quality of education and the

infrastructure provided has met national standards. In addition, each year Sekolah Juara students are able to make achievements both at national and international levels. Based on this background, this study is intended to get an overview of the contribution and potential of the Indonesia Juara Foundation in efforts to equalize the quality of education for the poor in Indonesia.

2. Methods

This research method is conducted using a qualitative approach with case study research design. Case study research design is used as a research design which is found to look at various cases, specifically to evaluate, where researchers conduct a thorough analysis of the case.¹⁰ Data collection in this study was conducted with interviews, observation, and secondary data collection from the Indonesian Juara Foundation. The sampling method in this study was conducted by purposive sampling method. Purposive sampling is, choosing specifically, people, or activities chosen intentionally in providing information clearly and relevant to the questions and objectives needed by the author, and the information needed will be obtained through other informants.¹¹ The informants are the management of Indonesia Juara Foundation. Subsequent data collection by retrieving findings data obtained from secondary data sources, namely notes from the Sekolah Juara program at the Indonesia Juara Foundation. The analysis carried out is by way of calculating data, displaying data, and summarizing the findings data in the field and secondary data obtained from the Indonesia Juara Foundation (Miles & Huberman, 1994).¹² This research was carried out at the central of Indonesia Juara Foundation that address is at Jl. Rajamantri Kaler I No. 45, Turangga, Bandung, West Java, Indonesia.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Indonesia Juara Foundation

Indonesia Juara Foundation was established on June 16, 2009 under the name Yayasan Rumah Juara Indonesia, and at that time chaired by Heny Widiastuti. Until 2018, Indonesia Juara Foundation has undergone four management changes, namely Heny Widiastuti (2009-2011), Muhammad Sobirin (2011-2012), Arif Taat Ujianto (2012-2017), and Muhammad Sobirin (2017-present).

Indonesia Juara Foundation has core business in two fields, namely schools and scholarships. Until 2018, 15 elementary schools, 2 junior high schools and 1 vocational school were established, each of which was spread in several major cities in Indonesia. While scholarship programs are spread throughout Indonesia through 30 branches of distribution of the Indonesia Juara Foundation.

3.1.1. Vision and Mission of Indonesia Juara Foundation

- Vision
Institutions empowering quality education for all
- Mission
 1. Scored superior and winner generations
 2. Managing education programs professionally
 3. Building synergy with various parties

3.2. Sekolah Juara

Sekolah Juara was established in 2007 as a response and a form of concern for the high cost of education. At that time, the program was planned and managed directly by the Education Division of the Directorate of Zakat Houses Program.¹³ The first school built was SD Juara Bandung. Then in the following years Sekolah Juara were established in several other cities.

Tabel 1. Milesones of Sekolah Juara's Establishment

Year	Level	City	Name of Sekolah Juara
2007	Elementary School	Bandung	SD Juara Bandung
2008	Elementary School	Cimahi	SD Juara Cimahi
2008	Elementary School	Jakarta Barat	SD Juara Jakarta Barat
2008	Elementary School	Pekanbaru	SD Juara Pekanbaru
2009	Elementary School	Jakarta Selatan	SD Juara Jakarta Selatan
2009	Elementary School	Medan	SD Juara Medan
2009	Elementary School	Surabaya	SD Juara Surabaya
2009	Elementary School	Yogyakarta	SD Juara Yogyakarta
2010	Elementary School	Jakarta Timur	SD Juara Jakarta Timur
2010	Elementary School	Semarang	SD Juara Semarang
2010	Junior High School	Bandung	SMP Juara Bandung
2011	Vocational School	Subang	SMK Juara Subang
2012	Junior High School	Pekanbaru	SMP Juara Pekanbaru
2013	Elementary School	Jakarta Utara	SD Juara Jakarta Utara
2014	Elementary School	Cilegon	SD Juara Cilegon
2016	Elementary School	Batam	SD Juara Batam
2016	Elementary School	Tangerang	SD Juara Tangerang
2017	Elementary School	Jayapura	SD Juara Jayapura

The number of Sekolah Juara students from 18 schools per 2018/2019 school year consists of 1,792 elementary students, 312 junior high school students, and 70 vocational students.

3.2.1. Education and Service Facilities

Parents of students are not charged any tuition fees so that all educational facilities and Sekolah Juara's services can be accessed for free. The free facilities include tuition fees, extracurricular activities, school uniforms, textbooks, field trip activities, parenting, and home visits.¹⁴

3.2.2. Education Curriculum

Sekolah Juara collaborates two types of curriculum, namely the curriculum of National Education Agency and the typical curriculum of Sekolah Juara. The typical curriculum of Sekolah Juara includes:

- Education / habituation of winner characters listed in the "core value of the Sekolah Juara".
Before starting teaching and learning activities, students are required to take part in self-conditioning activities. This activity is intended to instill spiritual value in the students. Forms of habituation activities include reading al-matsurat, tasmi Qur'an, listening to inspirational stories, and other activities.
- Development of potential students through multiple intelligences
Sekolah Juara do not apply a selection process that is oriented towards academic value at the previous level as well as schools in general. The absolute requirement that must be fulfilled by prospective students is poor people. Every child is considered to have intelligence potential that can be explored and developed maximally through multiple intelligence.
- Al-Qur'an Education
All students are facilitated with Al-Qur'an learning activities so that after graduation they are expected to have memorization of 1 juz for elementary school level, 3 juz for junior high school level, and 30 juz for vocational school level.

3.2.3. *Mandatory and Optional Extracurricular*

In addition to academic and spiritual aspects, students are also given compulsory extracurricular and optional self-development facilities. Compulsory extracurricular activities are scouts, while extracurricular choices include *pencak silat*, archery, basketball, futsal, drawing, little doctors, choirs, and others.

3.2.4. *Parental Involvement*

To achieve the goals of the Sekolah Juara effectively, there is a need for collaboration between schools and parents. The form of cooperation is implemented into parenting which must be followed by all parents of students every once a month. Parenting activities are intended to help parents manage and solve children's problems.¹⁵ In addition, parents are expected to be good examples for their children.

3.2.5. *Development and Training of Educators*

Every once a month, Sekolah Juara educators are provided with educational training facilities whose technical implementation is left to each school. The development and training of educators is directed towards improving quality which in turn will increase productivity.¹⁶

3.2.6. *Achievements*

Starting from 2010 to 2018, Sekolah Juara students who passed the National Examination reached 100% with a composition of 800 elementary school students, 376 junior high school students, and 42 vocational high school students.

A total of 20 Sekolah Juara alumni from the first to third generation are currently studying at several state universities, including Bogor Agricultural University (2 people), Bandung Institute of Technology (2 people), Andalas University (4 people), Riau University (1 person), Padjadjaran University (8 people), and Indonesian Education University (3 people).

Also this year, Sekolah Juara students have been able to score 343 achievements in various national and international competitions in the academic and non-academic fields..

4. **Conclusions and Recommendations**

Through the Sekolah Juara program, the philanthropic institution, Indonesian Foundation Juara has proven that quality education can be accessed by the poor for free. This quality is reflected in the education curriculum that collaborates between the National Education Agency's curriculum and the typical curriculum of Sekolah Juara, extracurricular and optional self-development facilities, parental involvement through coaching programs, teaching staff development and training, and achievement of the students.

This research is expected to be a guideline and reference for the wider community for the contribution of philanthropic institutions in Indonesia in eradicating education problems. Given the magnitude of the potential of the use of *zakat*, *infaq* and *shodaqoh*, the Muslim community is expected to be able to foster awareness to contribute to the equitable quality of education for poor people in Indonesia by donating a portion of their wealth through *zakat*, *infaq* and *shodaqoh*.

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